

Including participation requirements into planning law: experiences from the Netherlands

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Abstract

This paper analyses how ambitions to enhance participation in spatial planning decisions were translated into the new Environment and Planning Act in the Netherlands that took effect in 2024. The study analysed the various ambitions for enhancing participation and compared the participation requirements before and after the legal reform. The study showed that participation requirements hardly changed. Despite ambitions to enhance participation through new legislation, new rules do not regulate the content of the participation process beyond the requirement that were into force before the new act took effect. The study shows the limitations of codifying open concepts like participation in law: when it is not completely clear what and how should be realised, it will be impossible to define clear rules to structure specific practices. In turn, ambiguous rules can result in the reproduction of social inequalities by means of planning processes.

Keywords

Law, development, participation, planning law, planning reform

Introduction

The importance of participation for enhancing legitimacy and equitableness of governance and decisions is widely established in academic literature and planning practices (Newig et al., 2023; Leino & Puumala, 2021; Tolnov Clausen et al., 2021; Laskey & Nicholls, 2019; Koschkämper et al., 2016; Bäcklund et al., 2014). Participation also plays a role in making planning more inclusive (Stapper, 2022). Among other things, the debate about participation is about the way participation can institutionalise so that it can be used to secure the interests and

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suggestions of third-parties in decisions (Jager et al., 2020; Boeve & Groothuijse, 2019; Reed, 2008).

The will to enhance participation is reflected by the legal codification of participation requirements into legislation at different levels. The European Union has, for example, obligated public participation in decisions relating to the environment via the Aarhus treaty. Participation requirements can furthermore be codified in national legislation (e.g. Bäcklund et al., 2014) and local policies (Boeve & Groothuijse, 2019; Bakker et al., 2012). Such codifications typically express that participation should take place. The form and impact of participation often remain opaque. Although the importance of participation is stressed, the methods and objectives remain open and regulations rarely prescribe particular participation processes (Verhoeven & Bröer, 2015; Bakker et al., 2012; Edelenbos & Klijn, 2006). The openness of legislation is not surprising, as participation is a broad concept with diverse meanings in different contexts (Dral et al., 2023; Leino & Puumala, 2021; Reed et al., 2018; Wesselink et al., 2011). Furthermore, the meaning of participation is continually in flux and there are ongoing discussions about how participation can produce positive outcomes.

Despite the widely shared ambition to enhance participation, various studies have also shown that participation processes do not always produce the expected results (Reed et al., 2018; Wilker et al., 2016; Wesselink et al., 2011). Studies show that a history of previous participation processes, power differences, and intensity of participation all contribute to the success or failure of participation (Bell & Reed, 2022; Reed et al., 2018; Wilker et al., 2016; Wesselink et al., 2011). Involving participants in a way different from what they envisaged makes participatory processes unsatisfactory (Wilker et al., 2016). Newig et al. (2023) summarise that communication, the amount of power delegation to participants and stakeholder representation determines the extent to which a participatory process satisfies the needs of participants and decision-makers.

Two main aspects of participation gain particular attention in academic literature. The first is the extent to which participation is inclusive and supports decision-making that takes community wishes into account (Dral et al., 2023; Bell & Reed, 2022; Tolnov Clausen et al., 2021; Laskey & Nicholls, 2019; Koschkämper et al., 2016; Bäcklund et al., 2014; Reed, 2008). Pieterse (2022) and Stapper (2022) state that participation often collapses to a procedural formality that legitimises pre-decided agendas rather than setting the frameworks for decisions (that affect marginalised groups). The second is the extent to which the design of participatory processes explains their results (Dral et al., 2023; Newig et al., 2023; Bell & Reed, 2022; Leino & Puumala, 2021; Laskey & Nicholls, 2019; Reed et al., 2018; Wilker et al., 2016; Reed, 2008; Few et al., 2007).

This research for examples pays attention to different methods of participation and the influence participants can and do have on decision-making.

Although there is a fair amount of research on the different factors that influence participation processes and their outcomes (see e.g. Bell & Reed, 2022), little attention has been given to the ways in which these factors are included in regulations for participation. This translation of participation ambitions into rules deserves attention because regulations partly shape participation practices and experiences. This paper aims to address this gap and to provide an answer to the main research question: How are ambitions to enhance participation in spatial planning decisions translated into legal requirements? Answering this question provides insight in ambitions to enhance participation, the way these ambitions are translated into more specific requirements and the codification of these requirements into regulation.

To answer this question, we studied the formulation of the Environment and Planning Act, hereafter abbreviated to EPA. The EPA is the main planning act of the Netherlands that came into force on 1 January 2024. The EPA provides the framework for all decisions concerning the physical environment. Consequently, the EPA is intended to integrate spatial planning and environmental considerations. The impetus for EPA development stems from the assertion that pre-EPA planning law was inadequately oriented towards facilitating (sustainable) initiatives. Moreover, the EPA is designed to expedite and enhance the decision-making process (Ministerie van Infrastructuur en Milieu, 2011) and in that context stimulating participation and devising participation requirements became an ambition to be achieved by EPA development.

The main research question is divided into three sub questions: (1) What ambitions and definitions of participation are in use? (2) Which changes in ambitions and definitions occur during the formulation of a new planning act? (3) Which reasons substantiated codification choices?

The next section describes our research approach, materials and method. Section three presents our results. In section four the results are discussed and the paper ends with an overview of the main conclusions.

Research Approach

This section describes our analytical point of departure for the empirical analysis and connects this to our research method.

Analytical Framework

Ambitions to enhance participation are the starting point for this research. The broadness of participation means that ambitions for participation can be expressed in various ways and be

affected by previous choices (Stapper, 2022). Ambitions to change something (in this case making planning more participatory) are related to definitions of the elements that needs to be changed (in this case participation). Those definitions determine the scope and direction of the envisaged change (Berger & Luckmann, 1966). Definitions are followed by a translation to requirements. In the case of participation, these requirements are laid down in law (the EPA). When laid down in law, the requirements will, one way or the other, affect planning practice since formal institutions like laws co-constitute planning practice and the other way round (Buitelaar et al., 2011).

According to Buitelaar et al (2011) planning is an institutionalised field in which authorities, private parties, societal organisations and citizens interact. These interactions are guided by formal rules and informal practices (like negotiation and participation). These interactions are not free of values, but touch upon questions related to the distribution, access to and mandate over the physical living environment (Van der Krabben et al., 2011). Laws, like the EPA, are formal means for coordinating and structuring these different interactions. The EPA underscores the importance of early participation, which implies a reinterpretation of the more informal interactions in planning and the rules of the game for such interactions. The underscoring of the apparent importance of participation in the EPA raises questions about the access to decision-making and the conditions under which access is given. In this context, participation is both a democratic mechanism that is based on inclusivity and legitimacy, as well as a policy instrument that is based on efficiency and societal acceptance of decisions. Dominant actors have more (institutional) power in such processes than participating citizens or other parties (Buitelaar et al., 2011). While the EPA pretends to offer more opportunities for participation (Ministerie van Infrastructuur en Milieu, 2015; Ministerie van Infrastructuur en Milieu, 2011), Buitelaar et al. (2011) point to the level of congruence between planning law and planning practice as determinant for the effectiveness of law reform. When there is less congruence and a change of behaviour of planning practitioners is required, the contents of legislation become determining for the extent in which law reform achieves its ambitions. Less congruence and requiring a change of the behaviour of planning practitioners means that initiators and third-parties have no guarantee that similar cases are treated alike since this depends on the level of congruence and behavioural change (Buitelaar et al., 2011). When regulations and behaviour solely align with market logics, they run the risk of not advancing social justice (Pieterse, 2022).

With regard to participation, Bell & Reed (2022) deal with the ways in which participation creates more inequality and less effective decision-making when participation does not match the context of the issue at hand and lacks checks and balances. To achieve the desired

enhancement of decision-making, that is taking decisions that use and respect the input of participants, participation needs to be institutionalised so that it becomes more than a policy concept (Reed, 2008). Thus, there is a relationship between participation, planning practice and legislation governing planning practice. In this case, the EPA wants to provide more room for participation, but providing room demands more than legal requirements. It demands a planning practice that welcomes participation and can work with the input yielded by participation. If participation is not welcomed or when the input from participants is not used, inequalities can arise. The relation thus involves a tension between what participants expect, what planning practitioners can and want to do, and what legislation stipulates. Legislation that claims to offer more opportunities for participation, like the EPA, also raises questions about the ways in which legal certainty, power relations and inclusivity play a role in participation and the legislation governing participation.

The way in which participation is defined shapes that way in which participation requirements are formulated. Definitions of participation share their focus on involving organisations and individuals in the preparation of collectively binding decisions before a draft decision is taken by a party or parties other than the one(s) making or requesting the decision(s). Newig et al. (2023), Jager et al. (2019), Wesselink et al. (2011) and Few et al. (2007) conceptualise participation as engaging third parties in the parts of decision-making processes that are designed by statutory actors, before a (draft) decision is taken. Reed (2008) takes a somewhat broader perspective, arguing that participation needs to take place from the early phases of a decision-making process and subsequently throughout the process.

Figure 1 summarises the framework that we used to analyse how participation was conceptualised and translated into requirements. We focus on eight criteria to answer our central research question. The criteria are 1) clarity about participation goals (Reed, 2008; Few et al., 2007), 2) the implications of goals for the possible results, purpose and limitations of participation (Few et al., 2007), 3) accountability (Bell & Reed, 2022), by which we refer to the presence of a requirement to explain in general terms the participation process, 4) institutionalisation (Reed, 2008). In addition to these criteria: 5) clarity about the different steps in the participation process, 6) decisions on the inclusion/exclusion of actors, 7) written documentation, by which we refer to a specific form of accountability, and 8) the scope of participation are important. We add these criteria because they encompass the entire participation process. That process starts with setting the goal and scope, after which it can be determined who is responsible for (different parts of) the process as well as whether and on what grounds participation needs to take place. When these accountability and institutionalisation choices have been made, the participation process (steps in the process) can be designed and

decisions about which actors are allowed to take part can be taken. Participation finishes with recording the results. The participation process unites our criteria and provides opportunities to determine which parts of that process are mentioned in discussions about participation.

Participation processes can serve a plethora of goals (Edelenbos & Klijn, 2005) and without clarity about the goals, participation can become tokenism (Papadopoulos, 2012). The implications of the participation goal deviate with the goal itself. An unclear relation between participation goals and results is not clear can negatively affect the legitimacy of participation (Reed, 2008). Accountability is important because it creates legitimacy for administrators and can prevent participation from becoming a goal rather than a means (Innes & Booher, 2004). Institutionalisation is related to accountability in the sense that both call for continuous reflection on participation and the way it is carried out, given the results of participation (Bell & Reed, 2022; Leino & Puumala, 2021). Clarity about the different steps in a participation process provides guidance to participants and prevents ad-hoc decisions. A lacking process architecture can create insecurity (Quick & Feldman, 2011). The in- and exclusion of actors touches on the fundamental issue of representation and is therefore a criterion that can have deciding effects on the outcomes of participation processes (Young, 2000). The written documentation, especially analytical reports of participation, of participation process enables learning from previous processes, administrative accountability and academic analysis (Forester, 1999).

Not all aspects of participation will be translated into legal requirements. Participation has elements that are legal or non-legal in nature. Legal elements are for instance procedural requirements that can be laid down in regulation. Non-legal elements refer to elements that cannot be laid down in regulation, like the amount of trust between participants. Since we are concerned with law reform, we only focused on elements that can be translated into legal requirements. These are the criteria in our analytical framework. Our criteria do not focus on definitions of participation, but more general on perspectives on the design of participation processes. Legal elements can be categorised into elements that can be laid down in regulation, that should be organised in participation processes or that should be taken into account during actual participation. The organisation of participatory processes and actual participation are elements that are not prescribed at legal level since they are claimed to differ from case to case, see results.

Figure 1 – Analytical framework: participation definitions are analysed using eight criteria to answer the main research question

Process Tracing

The translation of participation into the EPA spanned more than a decade. The length of this process, in combination with the different and changing ambitions for and definitions of participation, complicates the assessment. The complexity is the result of actors bringing forward ambitions for participation that impact the discussions about participation requirements. These ambitions are influenced by for instance existing rules, procedures and methods (Mendes et al., 2022). Therefore, different ambitions for participation based on existing rules or concepts and ongoing interpretations are discussed and the ones that prevail are translated into legislation. With that, “trajectories of change and causation” (Collier, 2011, p. 823) emerge. Analysing pathways of development and causal relationships requires an assessment that unpacks a moving picture of institutional remaking, influenced by ongoing processes of interpretation, negotiation and translation. We therefore employ a research approach that enables us to understand sequences of events that shape the evolution of ambitions for participation and choices made about translating these ambitions into legal rules.

During EPA development several key documents were published in which participation ambitions and definitions were expressed. During the process ambitions and definitions with regard to participation were adapted in response to internal and external developments. To understand those adaptations, we systematically assess the (change of) ambitions and definitions against criteria for participation. The development of legal requirements is embedded in a historical, political, cultural and material context that delimits or enables transformation. Changes in this context occur during a process and can change the direction of the process

(Patterson, 2021; Pierson, 2004). A systematic assessment will reveal this (changing) context. We systematically assess by placing ambitions and definitions, and their change, in a broader and long-term timeframe that takes accumulation of events into account. Systematically assessing long term changes of law development processes enables understanding gradual changes that can occur during law development processes so that their effects on the (re)production and transformation of concepts can be explained in a way that does them more justice than a snap shot (Pierson, 2004). This means that the duration of the entire process during which participation definitions were translated to requirements has to be studied to see the adaptation, change and stabilisation (Pierson, 2004) of the concept and its interpretations.

This study uses process tracing to analyse the changes in ambitions during the formulation of the EPA. We focused our analysis on the period between 2008 (publication of the Elverding advice) and 2021 (the moment EPA development neared its finalisation) because this covers the entire period in which ambitions for participation were expressed and translated into requirements. Parliamentary and societal debates about the role of citizens in planning and governance (SCP, 2012; SCP, 2016) in this period made participation a relevant topic in EPA development. Process tracing allows us to systematically establish a long-term sequence of events and analyse how participation definitions evolved and were translated into specific definitions and requirements in policies and regulations. We traced the EPA development process and not the implementation process.

Methods and Material Used

We started by making a retrospect covering the period 2008-2021 to take stock of definitions of participation and equivalents in 42 documents that were published during EPA development. These documents included the EPA itself, its administrative orders (containing provisions that further explain the legal requirements in the act), an implementation act, amendments, motions, parliamentary reports and letters, minutes of parliamentary discussions, policy letters and advisory reports.

We focused on documents issued in the formal process of law making and the Elverding advice to assess their influence on evolving definitions of participation. Because we strictly wanted to focus on the evolution of definitions in the legislative process, we excluded non-parliamentary discussions about the EPA from our analysis. This for example includes advisory reports and opinion articles.

In the 42 documents we analysed the use of the word participation and found that several equivalents for participation were frequently used, namely citizen participation, involvement, deliberation and creating support. We included those equivalents in our analysis.

We identified participation definitions, highlighted important elements in participation definitions and compared the definitions of participation in the 42 documents and collected them in a document providing an overview of all definitions and proposed translation to requirements. Of the 42 documents, 23 are shown in the timeline (see figure 2), because these documents contained specific statements of politicians and experts that defined participation and/or set requirements for it, or because they show the governmental responses to those statements. In summary, a legislative process begins with the drafting of a bill that is eventually presented to the Lower House of the States General. The Lower House can change the bill with motions and amendments. After the bill is passed by the Lower House, the Upper House of the States General (senate), reviews it and members possibly issue motions in an attempt to change the bill. Based on that review, the Upper House accepts or rejects a bill. Upon acceptance, the bill becomes a law. After acceptance by the senate, the law can enter into force.

Based on the retrospect, the EPA development can be characterised by four distinct phases:

- 1) A pre-2011 phase. Reports and parliamentary documents published in this period later played a role in the law development. Formal EPA development started in 2011, the pre-2011 phase is the period ideas about the EPA began to take shape and evolved from the ambition to simplify planning law.
- 2) A phase covering the period between 2011 and 2016 in which the first draft of the EPA was developed and published for consultation. Also in this phase: the discussion of the EPA bill in the Lower House of the States General and the subsequent acceptance of the EPA by the Upper House of the States General (senate). So, in this phase, became a formal act.
- 3) A phase covering the period 2016-2018 in which the administrative orders were developed. Members of both Houses of the States General tried to change participation rules.
- 4) A phase covering the period 2018-2021 phase in which the implementation law and order, bylaws and orders were discussed in both Houses of the States General and reports about participation were published.

After collecting participation definitions and the proposed translation to requirements, we identified changes in participation definitions in the EPA and its administrative orders. We related the changes in participation definitions to the parliamentary discussions about the definitions of participation that occurred at the same time. We used the analytical framework (figure 1) to analyse which criteria were addressed in the 18 documents. We did not assess whether participation definitions met all criteria, but used the criteria to analyse if and how they are

addressed in participation definitions used during law reform. We use that to analyse how definitions were translated to participation requirements.

Figure 2 – Timeline showing key documents in EPA development

The EPA is the product of ambitions to among others simplify planning law, see the introduction. While broader in scope, we note here that ambitions to simplify planning law were taken up in the coalition agreement of the first cabinet Rutte (VVD & CDA, 2010). The second cabinet Rutte announced a bill to make this simplification tangible and this bill became the EPA (VVD & PvdA, 2012). Subsequent Rutte cabinets committed themselves to continuing EPA development and implementing the act (VVD, D66, CDA & Christenunie, 2021; VVD, D66, CDA & Christenunie, 2017).

Results

This section describes the results of our analysis, based on the process tracing. We summarise the most important findings per phase and assess changes in ambitions for participation and how these have been translated into specific legal requirements.

The EPA includes several instruments: 1) a strategic vision that focuses on long-term ambitions, 2) a programme that contains tactical-operational policies, among other to achieve ambitions from the strategic vision, 3) national (general) rules, these are rules set by the central government that roughly define how the EPA system should work and that are binding on third-parties, 4) decentralised rules that are binding on third-parties and determine how activities should be carried out, when national (general) rules provide opportunities to set decentralised

goals (the EPA zoning plan is an example of decentralised rule), 5) a project decision, which is intended for large and complex projects with a public interest and with which rules of lower authorities can be overruled. 6) an environmental permit, which is intended to realise actual projects and or individual activities.

Condensed Analysis

This section presents the most important results of the analysis of the development trajectory of participation requirements in the EPA.

Pre-2011

The development trajectory of the participation requirements in the EPA started before EPA development commenced: in a 2008 report (1 in our timeline) it was suggested to use participation to prevent delays in decision-making about infrastructure projects. The report suggested to use participation for creating support for intended decisions among the parties involved (Elverding Commission, 2008). The parties involved are the actors that are allowed to participate. The suggestions from the report were translated to law for infrastructure projects following a motion (2 in our timeline) (Samsom et al., 2009), that institutionalised participation for infrastructure projects of the national government.

Another motion (3 in our timeline) asked for better involving citizens in decision-making processes and substantial planning law reform (Pieper et al., 2009). The call for planning law reform resulted in the start of EPA development. Participation as a means to get more involvement of third-parties in planning decisions was giving a place in EPA development.

Before EPA development started, essays on the pros and cons of planning law reform were written (4 in our timeline). An environmental law expert suggested to not regulate participation using a one-size-fits-all-approach. Rather, the EPA should make it possible to adopt a tailor-made approach to participation (Koeman, 2010). With regard to institutionalisation a call was thus made to not regulate participation extensively.

2011-2016

A policy letter (5 in our timeline) issued in this phase did not operationalise participation by using criteria for participation (like the ones from the analytical framework) or describe how participation should take place. The policy letter did present participation as something that should be organised at decentral level (Ministerie van Infrastructuur en Milieu, 2011). Advisory organs of the government (6 and 7 in our timeline) emphasised the importance of leaving sufficient opportunities for tailor-made participation processes and thus called for little or none

participation requirements to be included in the EPA (Afdeling adviserend Raad van State, 2012; Raad voor de leefomgeving en infrastructuur et al, 2011). The institutionalisation of participation should thus leave open the way participation is given shape in practice. In their descriptions of participation, the advisory organs did not refer to criteria for participation, for instance the criteria from the analytical framework.

The EPA explanatory memorandum (8 in our timeline) stressed that participation needs to take place early in decision-making processes (Ministerie van Infrastructuur en Milieu, 2015), but does not clarify what is meant by 'early'. Stakeholders are apparently the actors that are allowed to participate. Besides stakeholders, the explanatory memorandum also describes that participation is something the public or citizens, enterprises and societal organisations should take part in. The actors that are allowed to participate are thus not yet uniformly described.

Another attempt to define participation (9 in our timeline) described participation in various ways and with various extents to which they allow for influence on decision-making. A uniform definition of participation has not been established. The minister responsible for EPA development did not want to formulate quality criteria for participation because that would hamper flexibility and make it less possible to come to tailor-made approaches (10 in our timeline) (Tweede Kamer der Staten-Generaal, 2015a). This reaction by the minister is a continuation of the line of reasoning from the previous phase. The reaction of the minister expresses the limited institutionalisation of participation.

Amendments (11 and 12 in our timeline) tried to introduce additional participation requirements (Dik-Faber & Mulder, 2015; Dik-Faber & Van Veldhoven, 2015). The amendments and the reaction of the minister to it (10 in our timeline) show diverging interpretations of the Elverding advice. While the parliamentarians presenting the amendments refer to the advice to state that participation increases support for developments, improves the quality of early stages of decision-making and accelerates decision-making, the minister referred to the report without explaining its interpretation of the Elverding approach. Participation was later delimited by the minister to the involvement that takes place prior to formal decision-making (13 in our timeline). Participation requirements were not set at national level because the minister stated that they can be set at decentral level (Eerste Kamer der Staten-Generaal, 2015), again limiting the institutionalisation in national legislation.

During the drafting phase of the EPA bill (8 in our timeline), limited participation requirements were included. Citizens, enterprises, societal organisation and governing bodies could suggest alternatives for projects requiring a project decision during the exploration phase (article 5.45 of the EPA bill and article 5.47 the EPA act), and comment on draft general

regulations via electronic means (article 23.4 EPA bill and EPA act), unless the Aarhus Treaty is met otherwise.

The EPA explanatory memorandum outlined that participation aims to align decisions with societal needs to reduce objections. The government preferred a flexible approach, expecting initiators to self-organise participation and competent authorities to tailor procedures to local needs (Ministerie van Infrastructuur en Milieu, 2015). Contrary to advice from the Council of State, the full Elverding approach was not legally codified for all projects but only for projects that require a project decision, again expressing the limited institutionalisation in national legislation.

Following discussions in the Lower House of the States General, additional requirements were introduced. Permit applicants must report whether and how third parties, the actors allowed to participate, were involved in participation (14 in our timeline) (Tweede Kamer der Staten-Generaal, 2015a); see also article 7.4 of the Omgevingsregeling. However, the EPA does not define "third parties" nor prescribe participation processes. In terms of the eight criteria in the analytical framework it remains unclear what participation is. The institutionalisation in national legislation remains limited too.

Amendment 11 proposed obliging authorities to specify how participation would occur, to reduce appeals (Dik-Faber & Mulder, 2015), see articles 5.47, 5.48 and 5.51 of the EPA. The amendment was rejected to preserve flexibility (Tweede Kamer der Staten-Generaal, 2015c). Amendment 15 in our timeline, seeking a universal duty to notify zoning plan changes, was initially rejected but later incorporated by means of a motion (Dik-Faber & Van Veldhoven, 2015; Tweede Kamer der Staten-Generaal, 2015a). Amendment 16 in our timeline, which aimed to oblige authorities to assist alternative suggestions, was also rejected due to the claim of the minister that the amendment made the role division between competent authority and initiator fuzzy (Tweede Kamer, 2015b; 2015c).

The Senate later raised concerns about unclear participation criteria. The minister reaffirmed that early, meaningful participation could reduce objections (Eerste Kamer der Staten-Generaal, 2015), and decentralised authorities were tasked with monitoring its quality. Participation remained undefined by strict criteria and the definition of participants (the actors allowed to participate) remained potentially broader in scope than the legal definition of stakeholders as used in the General administrative act (Algemene wet bestuursrecht). By referring the design of participation processes to decentral authorities and initiators, the minister did not have to operationalise participation. Participation is therefore not explained by means of criteria, for instance the eight criteria from the analytical framework. The institutionalisation of participation in national legislation remains limited.

2016-2018

In a second round of senatorial questions (Eerste Kamer der Staten-Generaal, 2016), concerns were raised about the clarity of the government's goals for participation under the EPA. Specifically, it was questioned whether the government sufficiently defined when stakeholder input is considered adequate. The minister reiterated that participation must occur early—before draft decisions are made—and stressed that competent authorities should design tailor-made participation processes. Authorities are now required to explain how participation was conducted and how input from citizens, businesses, and societal organisations was processed (governing bodies are omitted here) (Eerste Kamer der Staten-Generaal, 2016).

The rationale for emphasising this tailor-made approach to participation was to prevent participation from becoming a procedural checklist. Instead, the governmental aim is to ensure involvement and transparency by requiring organisers to account for how participation unfolded and its outcomes. With the formalisation of the EPA in 2016, these requirements were institutionalised through the Omgevingsbesluit (17 in our timeline) (Staatsblad, 2018).

The Omgevingsbesluit too emphasises a tailor-made participation approach by avoiding prescriptive methods or codes of conduct. Participation is defined as early-stage involvement of citizens, enterprises, societal organisations, and governing bodies (Staatsblad, 2018). These are the actors that are allowed to participate. The participation requirements in the Omgevingsbesluit aim to mitigate public opposition and procedural delays stemming from a more critical and digitally empowered citizenry. Referring to the Eilverding advice, early investment in participation is seen as a time-saving strategy (Staatsblad, 2018). The institutionalisation of participation requirements at national level remains limited.

Participation requirements are divided into three types of requirements, for the 1) Strategic vision, programme, and EPA zoning plan: Competent authorities must justify how participation took place and how it aligns with participation policies, as introduced by motion 23 in our timeline. For the 2) Project decision: Authorities must notify when participation begins and describe how third-party inputs and independent advice were handled. They must also provide participants with necessary information to ensure equal footing (18, 19 and 20 in our timeline). For the 3) Environmental permit: see subsection 3.1.4.

The overall regulatory approach remains consistent with earlier phases: limited institutionalisation at national level combined with encouraging open engagement to improve decision-making quality and speed. Participation is viewed primarily as a way to bring diverse societal interests into focus, though not necessarily to act upon them. Because the EPA lacks a uniform definition or process for participation, decentralised authorities and initiators are given

responsibility for shaping participation scope, participants, timing, and topics. Ultimately, the legislator prefers accountability, transparency, and context-specific flexibility over strict procedural mandates. The substantiation of the way criteria for participation (for instance criteria like those in the analytical framework) work is passed on to decentralised authorities and initiators.

2018-2021

With regard to the actors that are allowed to participate, this phase saw clarity about the stakeholders that are allowed to participate: Again, these are citizens, enterprises, societal organisations and governing bodies (Ministerie van Binnenlandse Zaken en Koninkrijksrelaties, 2019). This means that anyone and every organisation can participate.

The focus of the participation requirement that applies to the environmental permit is on initiators (21 in our timeline). Initiators must state whether participation occurred and, if so, report the results. The requirement becomes binding only if the activity deviates from the EPA zoning plan and is designated by the municipal council (Rijksoverheid, 2019). The requirement is connected to an amendment to the EPA implementation act (22 in our timeline). That amendment stated that the goal of participation is to increase the acceptance for decisions and introduced a requirement for decentral authorities to determine when participation is mandatory in case of permit applications for deviations from the EPA zoning plan (Eerste Kamer der Staten-Generaal, 2020a), see article 16.55 Omgevingswet.

A motion issued on the EPA implementation act (23 in our timeline) resulted in the necessity for decentral authorities to make participation policies (Eerste Kamer der Staten-Generaal, 2020b) see articles 10.2, 10.3a, 10.3b, 10.7 and 10.8 Omgevingsbesluit. The contents of these participation policies are not determined by the motion. The motion claimed that it is important for third-parties to have insight into local requirements for participation and that the government had not yet included guiding statements on participation requirements in the EPA (Eerste Kamer der Staten-Generaal, 2020b). The motion did not operationalise participation, for instance by means of the eight criteria in the analytical framework.

Assessing the Changes

The reconstruction of the EPA development brings attention to three main issues: 1 a summary of participation requirements, 2) a refusal to set quality criteria and 3) participation's place in plan development.

Requirements summary

Table 1¹ shows that the participation requirements should only apply when participation took place. Table 1 also shows that existing participation procedures got a broader scope due to legal changes. Our comparison therefore shows few rules and procedures that regulate participation beyond what was required before the EPA. With exception of the project decision, the EPA leaves participation voluntarily. Neither does the EPA not stipulate how participation should take place. Choices about participation are passed on to decentralised authorities and initiators. The participation requirements for the project procedure were copied from existing infrastructure law – in which they were included in response to the Elverding advice.

Different from existing planning law, the EPA introduced the obligation to account for the results of participation if it takes place. Furthermore, the EPA introduced participation requirements for permitting processes. The option to use participation if authorities change (parts of) general regulations is new too. The introduction of these rules is based on the expectation that participation improves the decision-making quality, restores trust in the government and accelerates decision making (VNG, 2019; Ministerie van Infrastructuur en Milieu, 2016a; Ministerie van Infrastructuur en Milieu, 2015; Dik-Faber & Mulder, 2015; Raad voor de leefomgeving en infrastructuur et al, 2011).

In the case of the environmental permit, the participation requirements function as a motivation requirement targeted at the permit applicant. In the case of the other EPA instruments, the participation requirements function as a motivation requirement targeted at the competent authority.

Table 1: Comparison of participation requirements

Instrument	Legal basis of participation requirement	Participation obligatory	Notification obligatory	Explanation of participation process and results obligatory	Possible to voice concerns competent authority
Strategic vision	10.7 Ob	Motivation requirement:	No	Yes, if process took place	Yes

¹ ¹ Participation articles are scattered over the EPA, a procedural administrative order and ministerial decree. For clarity, these legal documents are abbreviated in Dutch in the text of the article. The abbreviations mean:

Ow = Omgevingswet: EPA.

Ob = Omgevingsbesluit: EPA procedural administrative order.

Or = Omgevingsregeling: EPA ministerial decree.

		Free to choose for participation			
Programme	10.8 Ob	Motivation requirement: Free to choose for participation	No	Yes, if process took place	Yes
EPA Zoning plan	10.2 Ob	Motivation requirement: Free to choose for participation	Yes	Yes, if process took place	Yes
General regulations	23.4 Ow 10.3a Ob 10.3b Ob	Motivation requirement: Free to choose for participation	No	Yes, if process took place	Yes
Project decision	5.47 Ow 5.48 Ow 5.51 Ow 5.3 Ob 5.5 Ob	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Permit (comprehensive)	16.55, par. 1 Ow 16.55, par. 7 Ow 7.4 Or	Motivation requirement: Free to choose for participation	No	Yes, if process took place	Yes
Permit (limited)	16.55, par. 1 Ow 16.55, par. 7 Ow 7.4 Or	Motivation requirement: Free to choose for participation	No	Yes, if process took place	No

Table 1 shows different participation requirements set for EPA instruments, see also Boeve and Groothuijse (2019). This table shows that participation is a multifaceted topic rather than one process. The EPA sets no substantive requirements for providing input during participation or the processing of such input.

No quality criteria

The first draft of the EPA contained few participation rules to start with. While debates in parliament, to some extent, caused expansion of these rules, most discussions about laying participation down in rules were characterised by a refusal of the minister to set quality criteria for participation and a focus on general process rules instead. That requirements have been formulated as accountability mechanisms that only have to be taken into account if participation takes place demonstrates this refusal. EPA participation requirements did not introduce substantive criteria for assessing participation but only demand elaboration on the process. This makes it possible to let participation take place as information and consultation meetings, just as under pre-EPA planning law, and which has already been accepted in jurisprudence about the EPA (Court of Amsterdam, 2024; Court of Gelderland, 2024).

Rather than setting quality criteria, it was reiterated during the entire process of setting participation requirements in the EPA, the *Omgevingsbesluit* and the *Omgevingsregeling* that participation requires a tailor-made approach because the location, the (intended) decision, the scale of the (intended) decision, the EPA instrument, the context in which the instrument is applied and the potential participants always differ. This volatile set of variables is said to make it impossible to uniformly determine who participation should take place and what criteria apply. The parliamentary attempts to set quality criteria for participation were rebutted by the minister using the argumentation above (Eerste Kamer der Staten-Generaal, 2020a; Eerste Kamer der Staten-Generaal, 2015; Dik-Faber & Mulder, 2015) and did not refer to the building blocks of adequate participation processes we identified in academic literature. In terms of the criteria used in our analytical framework, participation was not approached systematically but mainly considered important on normative and policy level. Delineation on the participation goal, the implications of that goal, accountability and recording of the participation process in writing and actors allowed to participate took place. The other criteria were not explicitly referred to during the development of the participation requirements.

Place of Participation

Under the EPA the open consultation (mandatory for consulting other administrative bodies under pre-EPA planning law, following article 3.1.1 of the *Besluit ruimtelijke ordening*) can

still be used for providing the possibilities to react on concept plans. But, in the system of the EPA, open consultation can become part of participation or take place after it. The moment participation needs to take place is not made clear, as figure 3 demonstrates. It can function as a parallel process (which can be efficient since plan development can directly react to input from participation), or take place after plan development. This means that there are multiple moments at which participation can start and the EPA does not require start of participation at a predefined moment. This is emphasised by alternately presenting voicing objections as part of participation or excluding voicing objections from participation.

Figure 3 – Aggregated place of participation as introduced in the EPA, the period to voice objections (if applicable) is set by law at six weeks, other steps are not subject to a statutory deadline

Excluding the project decision participation criteria, the participation process does not have to meet specific requirements, nor start at a specific moment. Participation was an informal practice under pre-EPA planning law. The attempt to formalise this practice with the EPA has not gone far since the accountability mechanisms add little substantive criteria that complement existing informal participation practices.

Discussion

No Clear Definition

The openness of the EPA participation requirements can be explained as the product of intentions to stimulate participation without knowing exactly what should be stimulated and why. This matches findings by Korthals Altes (2016) who observed that EPA development was not based on an evaluation of current planning law, some essays on the potentials and pitfalls of planning law reform (Kuijpers, 2010) excluded. An evaluation of a previous translation of the Elverding advice to participation requirements into law did not take place. As a consequence, it is unclear what results were produced by those participation requirements or where those results offer improvement opportunities. The opportunities for improvement could have been starting points for more targeted requirements in the EPA.

The resulting generic and multi-interpretable concept of participation works as a means for connecting different (abstract) interpretations of participation and temporarily converging their meaning (Kooij et al., 2014). It is however too imprecise for translation into requirements because meanings can be attributed that counter intentions, which can be undesirable for authorities working with those regulations. For instance, in a situation that asks involvement of participants in the design of a new neighbourhood, an organiser of participation could limit involvement to informing or consulting and still present that as participation.

Over time, the Elverding advice became a point of reference for claiming that if participation requirements are included in law, decision-making will accelerate and face less opposition. These assumptions were put in the context of formal decision-making procedures that resulted in court cases with associated delays and costs. People however, forgot that the advice presented participation as part of a broader set of measures. This left the claim that participation could shorten decision-making procedures without any grounding.

Further discussions about participation focussed on small details in proposed rules rather than on the added value of those rules. A case in point is the limited reflection by the legislator on the critical note of the Advisory branch of the Council of State that translating substantial parts of the Elverding advice into planning law will not be effective. Moreover, it was not made clear how accountability mechanisms would contribute to the desired acceleration and acceptance of decision-making.

In the EPA case, the decision on how to organise participation is left to decentralised governments. These governments also need to set requirements that have to be met if they want to assess whether 'proper' participation took place. While this can produce specific participation requirements that match the local context, there are risks. The first risk is that requirements set by the government bodies annul the desired flexibility of planning regulations when the openness of EPA participation requirements lead to the use of self-devised conformance requirements (Gunn & Hillier, 2014). The second risk, mainly at decentral level, is that requirements start to differ among government bodies or cases without reasons for creating inequality. This inequality can disrupt planning processes (Laskey & Nicholls, 2019). The third risk is that the participation requirements in the EPA provide opportunities to limit participation to approaches that focus on legitimising decisions rather than enable critically discussing alternatives by limiting the scope of discussions or the contributions of participants (Tolnov Clausen et al., 2021).

While diverging definitions of participation, both at the level of the EPA and at the level of participation requirements set by government bodies, might provide leeway in individual decisions at first, it is this leeway that affects the legitimacy of the legal framework and the coherence of planning (Lees & Shepherd, 2015). The introduction of unclear concepts impedes

legal standards (Kukulska-Koziet, 2023). When taking a decision or when defending a decision in court, clarity has to be given about interpretations and incoherencies cannot be disguised

The question that remains after this study is how decentral regulation of participation requirements takes place in light of the challenges in formulating, implementing and enforcing local participation requirements sketched above. Decentral authorities organise participatory processes under pre-EPA planning law (Edelenbos et al., 2017). Such practices are not automatically changed by a new law (Buitelaar et al., 2011; Evers, 2015) and it is unsure how and to what extend existing practices can serve as input for decentral participation requirements under the EPA. Future research could be targeted at analysing the effects of the (decentral) interpretation of participation requirements for the desired acceleration and enhancement of decision-making.

Added Value of Participation Requirements in the EPA

Participation can serve different goals, like informing third-parties, creating acceptance for intended decisions or inventorying local knowledge (Edelenbos & Klijn, 2005). In this context, the legislator's emphasis on a tailor-made approach and the associated restraint in determining how participation should take place is explicable. After all, it is impossible to think of all the goals and possible uses of participation in advance and enshrine them in legislation. The tailor-made approach to participation contributes to planning decisions that recognise, respect and utilise regional differences; which happens to be one of the objectives the EPA should achieve (Ministerie van Infrastructuur en Milieu, 2015).

Legally mandating participation in the way it is done in the EPA might stimulate that participation takes place because the requirements that ask for an elaboration on the participation process might provide an incentive for competent authorities and initiators to think about participation and organise a participation process. The fact that the participation requirements enable this tailor-made approach means that participation processes can be targeted at diverse contexts, since participation needs in urban context might deviate from participation needs in more rural areas (Moore, 2022; Batten et al, 2015). Yet, it is up to local governments to tailor these participation processes, with all the associated work. Because society is becoming increasingly empowered and wants to provide input when decisions are going to be made, administrative bodies may feel morally obliged to organise participation. But as long as there is no project decision or designated environmental permit for deviation from the EPA zoning plan required, competent authorities and initiators are still not legally obliged to organise participation. Moreover, as described earlier, it has already been shown that participation may be limited to informing and consulting. Organising participation at the national

level, as it is done in the EPA, can have little added value given the fact that prior to EPA implementation participation in planning processes already took place (Edelenbos et al., 2017) and this process autonomously can result in the situation desired by the legislator.

Theoretical Reflections

We have focused on the legal requirements with regard to participation. On a more theoretical level, these requirements evoke the normative friction between juridical certainty versus legitimacy (Buitelaar et al., 2011; Hajer, 2003). The question is what the legitimacy of a decision-making process is when participation is limited to informing and consulting? The legitimacy is put under pressure by the desired flexibility of the participation requirements which in turn can create legal inequality, as explained in section 4.1.

During EPA development, participation was framed as a means for creating acceptance, preventing conflicts and enhancing the quality of decisions. Such expectations do not only act as a basis for the participation requirements in the EPA, but are also expressed in academic literature (Newig et al., 2023; Bell & Reed, 2022; Jager et al., 2020; Reed et al., 2017). It remains to be seen if these expectations will be met in practice. The EPA makes it a responsibility of competent authorities and initiators to decide on the form and extent of participation, without setting any criteria that need to be met. This implies the risk that participation in certain cases only becomes tokenism (Bell & Reed, 2022; Arnstein, 1969).

Planning is a policy domain for which the EPA provides the formal juridical framework. In this framework formal decisions, like allowing activities by means of EPA zoning plans or environmental permits play a pivotal role. Yet, planning is also a social and political process in which interests of third-parties, initiators and authorities intertwine and often collide (Newig et al., 2023; Reed et al., 2017; Hajer, 2003). Ambiguous participation requirements can result in friction between formal juridical frameworks and informal decisions. In turn, these two effects can lead to questions about who decides, where, when, about what and on the basis of what mandate?

The findings of this study are also relevant for international policies. The EPA, the Aarhus treaty and the directive on environmental impact assessments (European Union, 2012) stipulate that participation should take place without providing guidelines for the contents of participation and by mainly elaborating on participation from a procedural perspective. Like the EPA, the procedural requirement could address not only whether participation took place but also how and with what result. Like the EPA, a recognition of the fact that participation is a democratic means and no goal in itself that focuses on creating more acceptance could contribute to the design of participatory processes that support decision-making. The tension between

interpretable requirements and legal clarity needs to be recognised more. Legally mandated participation without any guiding principles on the content of participation processes can negatively affect trust in government. Both the EPA and the EU directive on the environmental impact assessment call for participation that is transparent, and in which all relevant actors and interests are involved. Their focus on the participation process does not guarantee that the desired inclusive and transparent process takes place. In the case of the EPA, this is due to a lacking operationalisation of the expectations that should be achieved with the participation requirements. Since specific requirements, for instance about the moment, influence or method of participation, are lacking. The lacking requirements confront us with a discrepancy between normative discourse and juridical reality. This discrepancy can contribute to participation taking place because it is seen as an obligation and without really connecting to the principles of the case and the desires of society (Fung, 2006). Rules that evoke associations that do not materialise in straightforward rights and duties can create problems of legitimacy. If such problems of legitimacy are to be prevented, the focus could be on 1) legally codifying minimum participation standards, for instance about timeliness, form and influence and/or 2) letting competent authorities explain why certain participation input was (not) adopted.

Reflections on the Method

The study focussed on participation as described in key documents in EPA development. The analysis could have been expanded by analysing descriptions of participation in non-parliamentary documents such as advisory reports, opinion articles, (governmental) websites, blogs and newspapers. The inclusion of non-parliamentary documents could have produced more insight in society's views on the expectations of participation that politicians held. It could also have provided more insight in what is considered important by society with regard to participation. Based on those insights it could have been analysed to what extent the accountability mechanisms match societal expectations or desires. On the other hand, this is perhaps an example of a comparison that should have taken place during EPA development instead of in this study.

Conclusion

In this study we analysed how ambitions to enhance participation in spatial planning decisions were translated into requirements in the EPA, the new Dutch planning act. The study showed that participation was laid down in requirements that only come into force once participation takes place and that existing requirements were re-used. For the remainder, the EPA does not include more specific requirements. The study also shows that different definitions

and understandings of participation played a role in the discussions, but that no clear definition was embedded in law. It therefore remains open what participation actually entails and this complicated the formulation of requirement that indeed enhance participation.

During EPA development it was recognised that each situation can demand specific participation requirements and it was generally feared that generic rules would reduce the flexibility for creating tailor-made solutions. Therefore, debates about participation did not focus on the specific requirements of timing, involvement, process or impact. Neither were more specific quality criteria discussed or translated into rules. Yet, for the safeguarding of public values standardisation and institutionalisation of discussions between public and private actors are beneficial. This standardisation and institutionalisation can start with setting minimum requirements, like quality criteria for participation combined with rules regulating the elemental core of dialogues and agreements (Pieterse, 2022). Nonetheless, the legal reform only introduced accountability mechanisms that come into force when participation takes place and generally leaves it to decentral authorities and even initiators of projects to choose to start participation processes, or not. This also implies that choices about the design and implementation of participation are shifted to local authorities. They become responsible for organising and assessing participation processes and for developing their own requirements that these participation processes should meet.

This study shows that retaining the possibility to devise tailor-made participation processes was important during EPA development. As a result, the formulation of precise participation requirements became difficult. Once it became clear that the formulation of these precise requirements was difficult, consideration should have been given to the added value of accountability mechanisms given their typically voluntary character and the fact that participation took place under pre-EPA planning law, which raised questions about the necessity of participation requirements. The re-use of existing requirements took place without an evaluation of the effects of these requirements. The lack of evaluation inhibits changing rules that existed in pre-EPA planning law in a way that helps removing common imperfections in participation processes. As in the reformed British planning system (Carpenter & Brownill, 2008) the participation requirements have the potential to make planning more inclusive, but neither enforce nor ensure it since the EPA participation requirements offer unlimited discretionary space for defining participation and designing participation processes. Moreover, the participation requirements in the EPA offer little legal certainty that participation will take place. Laws, after all, only change working practices when they are connected one-to-one with those practices and the informal institutions that define working practices (Buitelaar et al., 2011). When we focus on the letter of the law, we see the EPA not offering incentives to change planning

practice and validate participation. Since participatory practices already exist in Dutch planning practice, the EPA participation requirements can nonetheless institutionalise and generate positive results. But this will only work when the requirements are aligned with planning practice (Buitelaar et al., 2011).

The participation requirements in the EPA show the potential and limitations of translating ambitions to enhance participation into law. Making decentralised authorities and initiators responsible for participation implementations, because the legislator cannot know the local context in which participation will take place, means that they can devise a tailor-made participation process that caters to the needs of participants, which testifies of the potential of the requirements. But decentralised authorities and initiators have to define participation and devise participation processes themselves since it was not possible to define participation at legal level. Decentral authorities can to some extent set rules about participation that initiators have to obey, but they do not have full control over the organisation of participation processes by third-parties. As Pieterse (2022) and Stapper (2022) found: a lack of control over participation runs the risk that the process is stripped of its purpose and significance and decentral authorities are held accountable for something they cannot influence.

In the EPA, participation was not specified to what and how it should take place in different processes. The EPA does not include or exclude ways of involving third parties in planning decisions from being seen as participation. Co-designing a masterplan can be framed as participation just as easy as being informed in a plenary session. This shows the limitations of translating participation and other open concepts into law. If it is not completely clear what and how should be realised, codifying something in law seems pointless because legal changes do not necessarily change practices, especially not when legal rules do not match planning practice (Evers, 2015; Buitelaar et al., 2011). This codification becomes all the more pointless when it is realised that besides the EPA, other laws focus on involving third parties too, like a law focusing on the strengthening of participation in decisions by decentralised authorities. While this latter law is broader in scope than the EPA participation requirements, again the risk emerges that conflicts between the aims of both laws result in the EPA participation requirements not being endorsed and used as desired by the legislator due to a lack of congruence between law and practice and a failure to change organisational culture at decentral level (Buitelaar et al., 2011).

The EPA participation rules also show the amount of effort that decentral authorities have to put in creating a logical sequence of events. A typical development trajectory starts with contractual agreements between a government body and an initiator. Stapper (2022) shows that decision-making spheres shift from public meetings to contractual discussions since the 1980's. Many decisions are made in contractual discussions and only after that, participation starts so

that public involvement early in development trajectories is circumvented or postponed. That creates participation after points of departure have been set in contractual discussions. Contractual discussions involve the relevant government agencies and the private parties that will develop an area, but omit the typical participants like citizens or societal organisations. Firstly, those participants might experience a limitation of their input and influence on (intended) decisions due to contractual agreements. Secondly, decentral authorities have to be very clear about the scope of participation given contractual agreements. But a too narrow scope of participation can reproduce social inequalities when participants fail to bend to participatory process to their own objectives. When this mainly applies to participants that have access to politicians and the media, this can create inequalities too. Participation is also an element that parties can use to come to a shared understanding which makes it necessary to amend contractual agreements, thus making planning processes and the steering role of government actors more complicated (Pieterse, 2022; Stapper, 2022).

The article incorporates supplementary analyses and descriptions that, due to their extensive nature, could not be published as appendices. These appendices can be obtained from the corresponding author.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to thank two anonymous reviewers for their feedback.

Conflict of interest

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

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